

Open OnDemand Overview and Customization

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ABSTRACT

Open OnDemand Overview

Developed by the Ohio Supercomputer Center (OSC) and funded by the National Science Foundation, Open OnDemand (openondemand.org) is an open-source portal that enables web-based access to HPC services. Clients manage files and jobs, create and share apps, run GUI applications and connect via SSH, all from any device with a web browser.

Open OnDemand empowers students, researchers, and industry professionals with remote web access to supercomputers. From a client perspective, key features are that it requires zero installation (since it runs entirely in a browser), is easy to use (via a simple interface), and is compatible with any device (even a mobile phone or tablet). From a system administrator perspective, key features are that it provides a low barrier to entry for users of all skill levels, is open source and has a large community behind it, and is configurable and flexible for user's unique needs.

Relevance to the Gateways Community

OOD is currently installed and running at 1,600+ academic, governmental, and commercial HPC centers both in the US and internationally, including the University of Utah, Stanford, Pittsburgh Supercomputer Center, Tufts University, University at Buffalo, University of Arizona, Texas A&M, and NVIDIA,

and is actively being evaluated by many more. Most of these centers send representatives to the Gateways conferences.

The OOD team has held tutorials at multiple PEARC and Gateways conferences in recent years as well as regular online webinars, each of which have seen significant attendance of many dozens of people. As the Gateways series of conferences has historically had many attendees from locations that utilize OOD, as well as attendees from many of the most prolific science gateways development teams, holding another tutorial is a natural fit for the conference.

This proposed tutorial is meant to follow that same general format as utilized at PEARC and Gateways in the past with regards to application development and integration, with some key updates to reflect the changes in the Open OnDemand ecosystem over the past year.

A key differentiator of this year's BOF compared to previous years is that the Open OnDemand project has new funding from the NSF POSE program, which is designed to establish a new governance model for the ecosystem. Open OnDemand is in the process of establishing a steering committee and working groups, which is of significant interest to a large portion of the Gateways24 attendees.

An additional notable differentiator from previous years is the release in early 2024 of version 3.1 of the platform, that has many additional features that are of interest to the community, including integration with Globus and a new project manager.

Details of each of these key features will be included in the presentation.

Tutorial Overview:

This tutorial is meant to provide attendees with the basic tools to allow them to develop or integrate new applications into Open OnDemand. Nearly any software application can be made accessible via OOD. The official OOD github repo currently has links to software that appeals to a wide range of scientific disciplines, such as Jupyter, Abaqus, ANSYS, COMSOL, MATLAB, RStudio, Tensorboard, QGIS, VMD, RELION, STATA and Visual Studio. The OOD development team is also aware of planned or ongoing work to integrate many other software packages and platforms, including many that are prominent within the Science Gateways community, such as Galaxy, TAPIS, Globus, and Pegasus.

A general agenda is as follows:

Introduction to Open OnDemand:

~5 minutes (lecture & demonstration)

A very basic introduction to OnDemand will be presented to provide attendees with the goals of using OnDemand later in the session.

Open OnDemand Hands-on Introduction:

~15 minutes (hands-on activity)

The hands on walk through will provide details of how to use OpenDemand and serve as an example of user training. We will walk users through several steps including how to log in as well as using the Files, Job Composer, Active Jobs, Shell, and the File Editor App. We will walk users through a similar tutorial showing how to launch multiple interactive Apps. Participants will gain a working knowledge of how to use Open OnDemand.

Open OnDemand Customization:

~45 minutes (hands-on activity)

The instructor will walk attendees through basic configuration of the Open OnDemand dashboard. This will go through basic configurations like navigation bar color to more complex additions like adding html to the page. The instructor will then review how apps work with some detail to familiarize the participant with the concepts in this tutorial. The hands-on tutorial will then guide the participant through getting a Jupyter app to work in the environment. Participants will then extend and customize this app through detailed instructions.

Open Floor Discussion:

~20 minutes

The remainder of the time will be dedicated to open floor discussions and questions from the participants regarding specific ideas or issues they may have.

The tutorial will end with a short PowerPoint presentation that provides attendees with options for contacting the instructors and other software developers at OSC. We will also discuss future development plans, invite attendees to participate in the community, and answer questions.

Tutorial Logistics:

This is a 90 minute long, hands-on, step-by-step instructional tutorial utilizing a mixture of PowerPoint presentations, brief pre-recorded videos, and demonstrations. Attendees will utilize pre-configured Docker containers and materials published on GitHub to step through key aspects of the semi-automated installation/configuration process on their own machines. Because all the materials are publicly available, they can repeat the process outside the tutorial at their leisure and share it with colleagues.

Attendee Skill Level:

Intermediate

Tech Requirements:

Attendees must utilize their own laptop with the Docker client preinstalled and tutorial containers pre-downloaded. Docker experience is helpful, but not required. Linux command line experience and an understanding of HPC clusters and batch scheduling is required.

Keywords—Open OnDemand, App Development, HPC

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